

IMPACT DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF THICK
GRAPHITE-EPOXY COMPOSITE MATERIAL SYSTEMS

P. Pintado

Escuela Superior de Ingenieros Industriales, Seville, Spain
Currently Fulbright Fellow at ESM, VPI&SU

T.J. Vogler and J. Morton

Engineering Science and Mechanics
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Blacksburg, VA 24061

ABSTRACT

In this study, impact damage tolerance is evaluated for three different graphite-epoxy composite material systems which are fabricated as ninety-two ply composite plates. The systems are designated as brittle, moderately tough and interleaved (very high impact resistance).

When testing thick composites it is most important to use small specimens to minimize experimental costs. Square specimens (63 mm x 63 mm) are tested in an instrumented drop weight impact tower or in a high velocity gas gun impact device. Impact damage is inspected and comparisons are made between the two different types of tests, and between the three different materials. Residual strengths are measured on coupons cut from the impacted square plates and evaluated in interlaminar shear (three-point bending) and compression. Both tests show that for all three systems there exists an energy threshold above which the residual strength drops dramatically. The threshold for the interleaved system is higher than that for the tough system which in turn has a higher threshold than the brittle system. Dependence of residual strength with velocity was observed for the three material systems.

An effort has been made to differentiate between incident and absorbed energy in performing meaningful comparisons.

KEYWORDS: Thick Laminate; Low/High Velocity Impact; Damage Tolerance; TPB/Compression after Impact; Strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composite materials offer higher stiffness-to-weight and strength-to-weight ratios than traditional metallic alloys. These characteristics make them attractive for use in aircraft structures.

In particular, thick laminated plates are being used in wing roots as well as in aircraft engine fan blades. These thick structures are exposed to various impact threats ranging from the low velocity dropped tool to the high velocity encounters during flight.

In the past, the impact resistance of fiber reinforced composite materials has been a limiting factor to broad application. Research has been conducted to improve the impact resistance of these material systems and to better understand the mechanics of the impact process.

The ways in which the toughness of composite materials may be improved include the introduction of high strain-to-failure fibres, tougher resin systems and the use of compliant layers in between certain plies in the laminate. Also, the use of three-dimensional configurations, such as woven fabrics and stitched layers have been proposed for improving the impact resistance of fiber reinforced composites.

The understanding of the impact process is based on the knowledge of energy absorption and damage development. It is most important to characterize the energy dissipating mechanisms as well as the influence of the resulting damage on the residual properties of material systems. Morton and Godwin [1] present a detailed discussion of the different terms in which the impact incident energy can be subdivided. The problem of differentiating between material and structural response, complicated by the fact that structural response depends on incident velocity, is of great importance.

Models have been developed [2,3] to analyze the dynamic response of laminated plates and determine maximum load values and impact duration as a function of incident energy and missile mass. If impact resistance were to be determined using these models, then a failure criteria should be used to determine the incident energy for which first damage is initiated. The results would nevertheless be extremely conservative. The load values that the plate specimens can withstand without a significant drop in strength are much higher than those that create first damage.

Impact studies have been carried out on thin laminates whereas thick composites have received little attention due, in part, to experimental costs. A key idea when testing thick composites is the use of small specimens to reduce the high material costs resulting from a comprehensive experimental study.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Ninety-two ply composite plates were fabricated and provided by HEXCEL. Fiber orientations are 0°, 45°, 135° and 90°, but the stacking sequence is not exactly that of a quasi isotropic laminate. The closed form expression for the stacking sequence is:

$$\{[45/135/90_2/(45/135/0_4)_2]_2/45/135/0_5/45/135/90/45/135/0_2\}_s$$

The plates were fabricated from three different material systems:

T2C-145-F263

T2C-145-F155

T800H-145-F3900

T2C corresponds to Celanese Celion G30-500 fiber, whereas T800H corresponds to Toray T800H fiber. The number 145 refers to prepreg areal weight in gr/m^2 . F263 is designated as a brittle system and F155 as moderately tough. F3900 corresponds to the interleaved system. Even though the stacking sequence and prepreg areal weight is the same for all three materials, the curing processes give rise to different plate thicknesses: 13.4mm for the brittle, 14.8mm for the tough and 13.8mm for the interleaved.

The laminated plates were inspected under the microscope. In the tough system the individual plies were found to be porous and irregular. The interlayers in the interleaved system include spherical particles and are located between every two plies of the laminate (Fig. 1). In the brittle system the individual plies were uniform in thickness although there were local resin rich regions.

FIGURE 1. Schematic of the cross-section of the interleaved system

Square specimens (63 mm x 63mm) were cut from the laminated plates and supported in a 51 mm ring fixture. A 16 mm tup nose impacts on the specimen with energies ranging from 15 to 160 Joules. A Dynatup model 730 impact tester was used for the low velocity tests, and a gas gun was used for the high velocity impact tests.

The strength for the three different material systems (for undamaged as well as impacted specimens) was evaluated in three-point bending (TPB) [4] and compression, in both cases, the coupon dimensions are: 12.7 mm x 63 mm x t (where t is the thickness of the laminated plate). The long side of the coupons was aligned with the 0° fibers. In the case of residual strength measurement, the coupons were cut from the impacted square plates, making sure that the impact dimple is centered in the coupon.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Quasi-static tests on undamaged specimens Typical TPB load-deflection curves of undamaged specimens for each of the material systems are shown in Figure 2. It should be noted that, although the initial stiffness and maximum load do not vary considerably from system to system, the area under the curve, that is, the strain energy stored in the specimen prior to failure, increases significantly with the expected toughness of the materials, in other words, this quasi-static energy absorption capability is thought to be an indicator of the impact resistance.

FIGURE 2. Three point bending test on undamaged specimens for the three material systems

Typical compression load-deflection curves for undamaged specimens are shown in Figure 3. In this case the strength and strain energy stored in the specimens before failure is smaller for the interleaved system than for the other two systems.

FIGURE 3. Compression test on undamaged specimens for the three material systems

Quasi static loading of plates is carried out to find the strain energy stored in the specimens for this configuration. The test is a static counterpart of the impact process. Specimens are supported in the ring fixture and loaded through a 16 mm hemispherical tup. Typical load-deflection curves are shown in Figure 4. The initial stiffness is approximately the same for all three material systems but the strain energy prior to failure is significantly larger in the interleaved system than in the tough system which, in turn, stores a considerably larger strain energy than the brittle system. It is noted that the interleaved system is capable of bearing considerably higher loads after initial failure.

FIGURE 4. Quasi-static loading of plate specimens for the material systems

3.2 Low Velocity Impact

3.2.1 Load and Energy Records. The load record for a tough system specimen impacted with an incident energy of 44 J is shown in Figure 5. It may be inferred from the curve that the damage created in the specimen is limited or nonexistent since there are no sudden drops in load indicating an instantaneous change in stiffness. On the other hand, the load record for a tough system specimen

impacted with an incident energy of 89.1 J (Fig. 5) shows an initial drop in load indicating the creation of some damage, the specimen is still capable of bearing load and this starts building up again. When a certain value of load is reached, major damage is created and the load drops dramatically. The duration of the impact is an indication of the target stiffness, this stiffness is initially the same for both specimens, nevertheless, since one of them suffered severe damage during impact, its stiffness was reduced and the impact duration increased significantly (2 ms versus 4 ms).

FIGURE 5. Load records for incident energies below and above the threshold

FIGURE 6. Kinetic energy record for incident energies below and above the threshold

Energy records can be obtained from load-time signals. In fact, the contact force between tup and specimen is all that is needed to integrate the equations of motion of the falling weight if the assumption is made that friction with the guiding pillars is negligible. The equilibrium equation is: $ma = mg - P$, where m is the falling mass, a its acceleration and P the contact force with the specimen. The constant g is the gravitational acceleration. Time $t=0$ is the reference time at which $v=v_0$ (measured velocity), $x=0$ (displacement) and $V=0$ (potential energy). The acceleration record is integrated to obtain velocity and displacement, the potential and kinetic energies are then given by: $V = -mgx$, $T = mv^2/2$.

The kinetic energy records corresponding to the load signals of Figure 5 are shown in Figure 6.

Damage creation can be detected by the loss in kinetic energy.

3.2.2 Residual Strength. The TPB residual strength is plotted in normalized form as a function of incident energy in Figure 7. Normalization is performed, for each material system, with respect to the corresponding undamaged strength taken as the average of the strengths for five different specimens. The relevant features in this graph are the following. For each material system there exists a characteristic energy threshold above which the residual strength drops dramatically. The threshold for the brittle system is about 40J, that for the tough system about 60J, whereas the interleaved system shows a major drop in strength at about 90J. The residual strengths for incident energies above the threshold "stabilize" (but will be zero for very high energies at or near perforation) at different values depending on the material system: 40% for the interleaved system, 20% for the tough and 10% for the brittle system. The strength for incident energies below the threshold remains within 90% of the undamaged strength except for the brittle system that seems to have reduced strength (80%) even for very low energy levels. The conclusion to be drawn from this graph is that the interleaved system is significantly more impact resistant than the tough and brittle systems, it has a higher damage threshold as well as a higher residual strength after the threshold.

FIGURE 7. TPB normalized residual strength versus incident energy for the three material systems

Normalized compression strengths are shown in Figure 8 as a function of incident kinetic energy. The features described above are again seen in this graph. The damage threshold is about 25J for the brittle system, 70J for the tough and 80J for the interleaved system. The mechanisms triggering failure in the case of compression loading (fiber and sublaminar buckling) are different from those triggering TPB failure (interlaminar shear), therefore it is not surprising that the thresholds are not located at the same energy levels for both tests, moreover; it is of interest that they do not differ considerably. It is worth noting that, for the brittle and interleaved systems, there seems to be an increase in residual strength for low incident energy levels.

As mentioned before, the impact force data for each specimen can be integrated to obtain values of absorbed energy. The calculated absorbed energy values versus incident energy for each material system are shown in Figure 9. Damage thresholds are again seen in this graph. It is noted that, above the highest threshold, the energy absorbed by the interleaved system is higher than the energy absorbed by the other two systems, even though the residual strength was much higher for this material (40% versus 10% and 20%). The slopes of the curves for energies above the threshold indicate the increase in absorbed energy corresponding to a unit increase in incident energy, this

slope is higher for the interleaved system than for the tough and brittle system.

An elastic-perfectly plastic model would yield $E_A(E_i)$ curves that are zero up to a certain value of energy above which they deflect to run parallel to the 45° line (all increase in incident energy is absorbed and stored in plastic deformation). The threshold can be accounted for with the use of fracture mechanics concepts. In this case the curves are zero up to a certain value of incident energy for which the stresses are such that fracture is initiated, the step increase in absorbed energy corresponds to the energy required to create the initial cracks. For energies above the threshold, different slopes are obtained using different values of energy required to propagate the damage.

FIGURE 8. Normalized residual strength in compression versus incident energy for the three material systems

FIGURE 9. Calculated absorbed energy versus incident energy for the three material systems

Comparisons based on incident impact energy are useful in structural design where the starting point is the information concerning the likelihood of an impact of a given incident energy. However, there are other energy components that would better determine the reduction in strength, in particular, linear relations have been proposed to correlate the variation of residual strength with absorbed

energy. This linear relation has not been observed in this study (see Figures 10 and 11), an explanation for which is that the absorbed energy can be further subdivided in energy to create damage and energy dissipated by other means, furthermore, the propagation of damage may be such that the strength is not further reduced.

FIGURE 10. TPB normalized residual strength versus absorbed energy for the three material systems

FIGURE 11. Normalized residual strength in compression versus absorbed energy for the three material systems

3.3 High Velocity Impact TPB residual strength are measured for specimens of the three material systems when impacted using the high velocity gas gun. The TPB residual strength is plotted versus incident energy in Figure 12. The general characteristics mentioned in the previous section are again seen in the case of high velocity impact, however, there are differences observed between low and high velocity impact on the material systems.

It can be seen in Figure 12 that the tough system does not show a definite energy threshold. In fact,

it can be argued that the scatter is due to a bifurcation in failure mode; different values of strength are obtained depending on which failure mode was excited during impact. The two curves in Figure 12 represent this idea which, in turn, can account for the fact that some authors have reported dependence of the impact resistance with velocity whereas others claim no dependence. A bifurcation in failure mode means that for a given incident energy two different types of damage can be created depending on second order factors. One of the damage modes is critical when evaluating strength as interlaminar shear (TPB), whereas the other influences the mentioned strength less. A model capable of simulating such a bifurcation would have to be based on an extensive inspection of damage. The damage inspection performed in this study (Section 3.4) has not revealed evidence to support the bifurcation argument.

FIGURE 12. TPB Normalized residual strength versus incident energy for the three material systems. High velocity impact, 40 gr. missiles

The bifurcation phenomenon is not found in the case of the brittle system. A certain reduction in the energy threshold is observed when compared to the low velocity results. For the case of the interleaved system, the threshold seems to increase in the high velocity tests. However, this result is based on a very limited number of data points.

3.4 Damage Inspection As already mentioned, TPB and compression coupons are cut from the square plates as a 12.7 strip centered on the specimen. The removal of the coupon from the plate provides two surfaces on which damage can be inspected. A few specimens were impacted under different incident energies and cut through the impacted area to observe the damage under the impacting nose.

3.4.1 Interleaved System. Damage initiates as matrix cracking under the impactor. These cracks trigger the propagation of delamination cracks that run along different ply interfaces. Two very probable locations for these cracks are the interfaces between the first or second group of layers oriented along the 0° direction and the layers below oriented along the 45° direction. This type of damage is observed even for specimens with high residual strength and impacted with low energy levels (for which cases the delamination crack is closed and difficult to detect at low magnifications). For these cases, no damage can be seen on the top layers; that is, the matrix cracks under the nose of the impactor, if they exist, do not reach the observed section before the delamination crack does.

Surprisingly, the observed damage for specimens impacted with incident energies above the threshold is just an outgrowth of the type of damage described above. The delamination cracks are wide open and, in some cases, run along the whole length of the specimen. The top layers are severely damaged. The matrix is cracked in the central section of the specimen and in all layers from the top down to the delaminated interface. The delaminated layers are forced to open by a wedge formed by debris and groups of layers of the same orientation sequence as those below the crack. No damage is found below the delamination crack for any of the specimens examined.

3.4.2 Tough System. For the case of the tough system, no damage reaches the observed section for incident energies below the threshold. For incident energies just above the threshold, the type of damage described above is observed: a delamination crack below the first or second group of 0° layers and matrix cracks in the central section of the specimen. When the incident energy is increased, delamination cracks are observed at several other interfaces in the laminate.

3.4.3 Brittle System. The brittle system behaves in quite a different fashion. No damage reaches the observed section for incident energies below the threshold. Several delamination cracks are observed at different interfaces in the laminate for incident energies just above the threshold. This pattern does not change considerably when the incident energy is further increased.

4. DISCUSSION

When investigating the impact damage tolerance of thick composite material systems attention should be paid to the following questions. How is the incident energy used during impact?, that is to say, how much energy is dissipated and in what form? How does the structural response affect the comparison between materials?, in other words, how is it possible to separate structural response from material response? The question is of particular importance in the case of thick laminates for which small specimens should be used due to economical constraints. Is there any quasi-static indicator of the impact resistance of the different material systems? Can the results for low velocity be extrapolated to high velocity response?.

4.1 Energy Distribution Energy balance equations can be written when the different energy forms are taken as their values at the end of the impact event. The incident energy is divided into two basic quantities, the absorbed energy and the recovered energy:

$$E_I = E_A + E_R$$

The recovered energy is the kinetic energy of the striking object after impact. In the case where no perforation occurs, the recovered energy is a direct transformation of the strain energy stored in the specimen after all damage has taken place. The absorbed energy can be further subdivided into the energy that goes into the creation of damage and the energy that is dissipated in damped vibrations, carried away by stress waves or transformed into heat by friction:

$$E_A = E_D + E_V + E_{SW} + E_F$$

It is only the component of the absorbed energy that goes into the creation of damage that is of interest when explaining the residual properties of the impacted specimens, moreover, the different types of damage will influence differently the residual properties.

The variation of absorbed energy with incident energy ($E_A(E_I)$) was shown in Figure 9 for the three material systems. The absorbed energy increases with the incident energy for values above the threshold. The residual strength is almost constant with incident energy for values above the threshold (see Figure 7). Therefore, it might be suggested that the above mentioned increase in absorbed energy is dissipated in friction between the delaminated sublaminates or goes into the

propagation of damage that will not significantly further reduce the specimen strength. The observed damage supports this idea, the increase in absorbed energy is used in propagating and opening the already existing delamination cracks. The cracks in the interleaved system run through deflecting spherical particles, the energy to propagate this crack is higher than that to create a clean cut and, therefore, the slope in the $E_A(E_I)$ curve is larger (see Figure 9) than that for the tough system. The energy to propagate a delamination crack in the brittle system is very low, for incident energies just above the threshold the strain energy stored in the specimen is capable of driving several delamination cracks that dramatically reduce the strength of the specimen (see Figure 7), the resulting configuration is very elastic, any further increase in incident energy is recovered and the strength remains almost constant.

4.2 Structural response versus material response During impact, the kinetic energy of the striking object is transferred to the composite structure. Part of it is stored as local or global (structural) strain energy and the rest is dissipated. As the velocity of the striking object increases, the inertial forces in the structure become more important and the kinetic energy has to be stored or dissipated in a more localized region, the structure does not have time to respond to the external loads and the creation of damage is localized near the impacted area. It is clear then, that structural response and impact velocity are related and play an important role in the impact performance of composite structures.

It is not feasible to experimentally simulate all possible impact events for a given structure. Therefore, when ranking material systems, it is necessary to devise a test method capable of differentiating the impact behavior of the various systems as independently as possible of the structure in which the material is going to be used. This is achieved by using the same test configuration for all three material systems and making sure that they all have similar values of stiffness (and density). If this is the case, the dynamic response before any damage is generated will be a common constant for all material systems. The three systems investigated in this study have shown similar initial stiffness (see Figures 2 and 3), therefore the structural response does not play a role in the ranking of the material systems. This is of importance for thick composites because it allows to use a small test configuration for which the practical number of tests that can be performed increases considerably.

TABLE 1. Energy thresholds and strain energies prior to failure

MATERIAL SYSTEMS	Energy Threshold: TPB (1)	Energy Threshold: Comp.	Strain Ener. prior to failure: Plate spec. (2)	Strain Ener. prior to failure: TPB	(1)/(2)
Brittle	40	25	23.5	13.6	1.7
Tough	60	70	33.0	21.4	1.8
Interleaved	90	80	45.5	31.2	2.0

(First ply failure has been used in calculating the strains energies in Table 1)

4.3 Quasi static indicator Many authors share the idea that there exist a linear relation between impact resistance and the area under some quasi-static stress-strain curve [5,6]. The trend holds for the three material systems under study, that is, the damage threshold (for both TPB and compression) diminishes as the area under the TPB load-deflection curve grows. The linear relation is, however, not verified for these three materials. If the quasi-static loading of plate specimens is used to compare with the impact resistance (TPB), then there seems to be a linear relation between the energy threshold and the strain energy stored in the plate specimens prior to failure (see Table 1), the ratio between these two energy values is close to 2 for the three material systems. (The statement

can then be made that approximately twice as much energy is needed to significantly damage the specimen in the case of impact loading than in the static counterpart.

4.4 High velocity versus low velocity impact In every impact process there are two independent incident variables to which attention should be paid: the incident energy and the incident velocity. In the present study, rate dependency has been observed to a certain extent. The brittle system seems to embrittle (lower energy threshold) when the incident velocity is raised (see Figures 7 and 12). The tough system shows a peculiar behavior with velocity: there seems to be a bifurcation in failure mode resulting in "two" residual strength curves. The interleaved system seems to have an improved impact resistance at high velocities (see Figures 7 and 12).

5. CONCLUSIONS

A test configuration that allows the use of small specimens has been devised. Low velocity as well as high velocity impact tests have been performed on three different material systems: brittle, tough and interleaved. For both types of impact, the interleaved system has superior impact resistance than the tough system which, in turn, has superior impact resistance than the brittle system. The energy levels to initiate and propagate delamination cracks in the interleaved system are higher than those in the other two systems, therefore, the incident energy at which a significant drop in strength is observed and the residual strength for higher energy levels are larger for this system. All three material systems show almost constant strength for energy levels above the threshold, the additional absorption of energy does not cause a reduction in strength. A peculiar residual performance has been observed for the tough system in high velocity impact tests. A bifurcation explanation has been proposed.

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6. REFERENCES

1. J. Morton and E.W. Godwin, Composite Structures, 13, 1 (1989).
2. K.N. Shivakumar, *et al.*, Journal of Applied Mechanics, 52, 674 (1985).
3. F.K. Chang, *et al.*, SAMPE J., 26, 18 (1990).
4. ASTM, "Standard Test Method for Apparent Interlaminar Shear Strength of Parallel Fiber Composites by Short-Beam Method", ASTM D 2344 - 84, 43 (1988).
5. M.W. Wardle and G.E. Zahr in S.L. Kessler, *et al.*, eds., Instrumented Impact Testing of Plastics and Composite Materials, ASTM STP936, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1987, pp. 219, 235.
6. K.J. Bowles in J.D. Whitcomb, ed., Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Eight Conference), ASTM STP972, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1988, pp. 124, 142.